

Exploring Exopolymeric Substances Production from Methane by Methanotrophic Bacteria

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Abstract

Methane can serve as a versatile feedstock for biotechnological processes, enabling the sustainable production of valuable bioproducts. In this study, an enriched methanotrophic microbial community was used to assess the production of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS). A set of batch experiments was conducted to assess the effect of methane concentration (2 gas mixtures mimicking natural gas and biogas) and 2 nitrogen species (nitrate and ammonium) on EPS production. Results show that the highest concentration of EPS was obtained when nitrate was added as nitrogen source and the use of biogas or natural gas did not have an effect. Also, the protein fraction of the EPS was the most affected when changing the nitrogen supply.

Keywords

Extracellular polymeric substances, methane, methanotrophic bacteria.

INTRODUCTION

Methane (CH₄) is the second most prevalent greenhouse gas (GHG) after carbon dioxide (CO₂), with a significantly higher global warming potential¹. Its concentration has been steadily rising, now approximately three times higher than preindustrial levels² making CH₄ a major environmental concern in the context of climate change³. Methane is also a key energy source, powering one-quarter of the global economy. It is the primary component of natural gas, which is predominantly combusted for heat and electricity generation. Additionally, methane is produced during the anaerobic microbial breakdown of organic matter, leading to biogas, which contains 60-70% methane. When burned for heat and power generation, biogas is considered a carbon-neutral energy source, especially when derived from renewable organic materials over a short time frame⁴. Due to the relatively low cost of methane, there is growing interest in using it as a carbon source for microbial conversion processes⁵. Methanotrophic microorganisms, which naturally catalyze many biochemical reactions at ambient temperatures and pressures, make methane conversion a potentially sustainable process. A methanotroph-based biorefinery, from a biological perspective, offers a powerful platform for producing value-added compounds⁶.

This abstract focuses on the production of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) from methane through an enriched mixed culture of methanotrophic microorganisms. Bio-based polymers are becoming more popular as alternatives to conventional petroleum-derived polymers. However, the sustainability of many biopolymers is debatable, given the land use required for growing raw materials, which could otherwise be allocated for food production. Biofilm exopolymeric substances (EPS), consisting of extracellular polysaccharides, proteins, and DNA, have recently gained attention as a promising option for resource recovery, owing to their ability to form polymer networks or hydrogels⁷. This abstract presents preliminary results on the effect of methane concentration and nitrogen species on the production of EPS by an enriched methanotrophic community.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An enriched methanotrophic microbial community developed for 1 year was served as the inoculum for this study. A set of batch tests following the conditions detailed in table 1 was conducted.

Table 1. Experimental conditions applied. Each test was conducted in duplicate.

Source of methane	Batch tests	Nitrogen
Synthetic natural gas (95% CH ₄ + 5% CO ₂)	T1_N	100-50-300 mg N-NO ₃ ⁻ /L
	T2_N	50-100 mg N-NH ₄ ⁺ /L
	T3_N	No nitrogen
Synthetic biogas (70% CH ₄ + 30% CO ₂)	T1_B	100-50-300 mg N-NO ₃ ⁻ /L
	T2_B	50-100 mg N-NH ₄ ⁺ /L
	T3_B	no nitrogen

All tests were conducted in fed-batch in 260 mL bottles, with 200 mL of headspace and 60 mL of aqueous phase. Initially, 50 mL of the enriched methanotrophic culture was added into the fed-batch bottles together with 10 mL of the nutrient solution containing the desired nitrogen species (either nitrate or ammonium and none depending on the test). The headspace was filled with an artificial atmosphere composed of pure O₂ and the CH₄ mixture (synthetic natural gas or biogas, depending on the test) in a 60/40 volume ratio. Samples of the headspace were taken after 24h of renewal, prior renewal, every working day. Liquid phase samples were taken every 2-3 days and immediately filtered for analysis of the nitrogen species. In those experiments where nitrogen was depleted, nitrogen was added again at different concentrations to test the population resilience to these nitrogen species. The tests lasted for 265h and biomass samples for EPS analysis were taken at 96h and at the end of the tests.

EPS extraction was done following the formaldehyde and sodium hydroxide (HCO-NaOH) method¹¹; polysaccharides and proteins were analyzed^{12,13} for its characterization and ATP was analyzed to assess intracellular contamination.

RESULTS

The gas composition of the headspace of the different batch tests during the first week is presented in Figure 1. The column of the cycle 0 represents the gas composition after each replacement of the gas headspace.

Figure 1. Evolution of the artificial atmospheres after 6 cycles of 24h each. Replicates are grouped according to nitrogen source, if any. a) T1_N b) T2_N, c) T3_N, d) T1_B, e) T2_B, f) T3_B.

While the batch tests with nitrate as a nitrogen source consumed most of O₂ available and part of the CH₄, those with ammonia performed worse regarding oxygen and CH₄ consumption corroborating that nitrate is the optimal source of nitrogen for the methanotrophic population growth, as it has been described previously in literature¹⁷. It is theorized that this effect could be produced by the competitive interaction between ammonia and the methane monooxygenase (MMO)¹⁸.

Nitrate was consumed during the whole duration of the tests independently of the concentration added (Figure 3a). However, ammonium was only consumed when its concentration was initially at 50 mg N/L and stopped when the concentration was increased to 100 mg N/L (Figure 3b). No nitrite or nitrate was detected in experiments where ammonium was supplied. Currently more tests are underway to further explore the role of ammonium in the methanotrophic metabolism.

Figure 2. Nitrogen profiles during the different tests conducted: a) with nitrate; b) with ammonia. At times 48 and 96h, the respective nitrogen source was added.

An increase in EPS content from the first to the second week was detected, being the protein fraction of EPS in treatments with NO_3^- the most benefited (Figure 3). Even so, the polysaccharide fraction of the replicates fed with biogas and nitrate was increased as well. Nonetheless, the ratio EPS:biomass concentration (data not shown) suggests that the main cause of the EPS increase over the experiment might be attributed to bacterial growth. This would prove NO_3^- as the best option for methanotrophic growth but not for the direct increase of EPS production. EPS can vary depending on its source very much, and protein dominated EPS is not rare. However, polysaccharide enriched EPS is preferred to obtain useful biopolymers that can later be used to produce different products. Our current experiments are not only focusing on increasing the total EPS content but also enhancing the polysaccharide fraction. The results obtained will be also presented at the conference. No difference between the NH_4 and the nitrogen deprived replicates was seen. Finally, the use of natural gas or biogas had no effect on the EPS concentration obtained.

Figure 3. EPS concentration obtained for each batch test at 96h (first column) and at 265h (end of the experiment, second column).

PRELIMINARY CONCLUSIONS AND FOLLOW UP EXPERIMENTS

The experiments presented in this study lead to the following preliminary conclusions:

1. Nitrate is the preferred tested nitrogen source by the methanotrophic bacteria enrichment used. Nitrate was consumed under all concentrations tested together with methane consumption and oxygen depletion, indicating biomass growth.
2. Ammonium consumption was detected at concentrations lower than 50 mg N/L, although the consumption of methane and oxygen was lower as compared to the experiments with nitrate. Concentrations of 100 mg N-NH₄/L inhibited the methanotrophic biomass, detecting neither consumption of ammonium, methane nor oxygen.
3. EPS concentration only increased during the second week of operation in the batch tests receiving nitrate. The protein fraction of the EPS was the most increased while the polysaccharide fraction remained relatively constant.

More experiments are underway to assess the effect of pH on EPS production and to understand the role of ammonium in methanotrophic metabolism.

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REFERENCES

1. Lynn J et al., 2021. Communications in the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report cycle. *Clim Change*. doi: 10.1007/s10584-021-03233-7.
2. Saunio M. et al., 2020. The Global Methane Budget 2000–2017, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 12, 1561–1623, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-1561-2020>, 2020.
3. Etminan M. et al., 2016. Radiative forcing of carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide: A significant revision of the methane radiative forcing: GREENHOUSE GAS RADIATIVE FORCING. *Geophysical Research Letters*. 43. 10.1002/2016GL071930.
4. Hanson, R. & Hanson, T. 1996. Methanotrophic bacteria. *Microbiol. Rev.*, 60(2), 439.
5. Lee, E.Y. 2019. *Methanotrophs: Microbiology Fundamentals and Biotechnological Applications*, Springer.
6. Kalyuzhnaya MG et al., 2015. Metabolic engineering in methanotrophic bacteria. doi: 10.1016/j.ymben.2015.03.010.
7. Feng C. et al., 2021. Extracellular biopolymers recovered as raw biomaterials from waste granular sludge and potential applications: A critical review doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.142051.
8. Pikaar I. et al., 2018. Decoupling Livestock from Land Use through Industrial Feed Production Pathways. *Environ Sci Technol*. doi: 10.1021/acs.est.8b00216.
9. Areniello M. et al., 2023. Biowaste upcycling into second-generation microbial protein through mixed-culture fermentation. *Trends Biotechnol*. doi: 10.1016/j.tibtech.2022.07.008.
10. Hülsen T. et al., 2018. Simultaneous treatment and single cell protein production from agri-industrial wastewaters using purple phototrophic bacteria or microalgae – A comparison, *Bioresource Technology*. doi: 10.1016/j.biortech.2018.01.032.
11. Liu H. et al., 2002. Fang HH. Extraction of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) of sludges. *J Biotechnol*. doi: 10.1016/s0168-1656(02)00025-1.
12. Dubois M. et al., 1951. A colorimetric method for the determination of sugars. *Nature*. doi: 10.1038/168167a0. PMID: 14875032.
13. Peterson GL., 1977. A simplification of the protein assay method of Lowry et al. which is more generally applicable. *Anal Biochem*. doi: 10.1016/0003-2697(77)90043-4.
14. Love MI. et al., 2014. Moderated estimation of fold change and dispersion for RNA-seq data with

- DESeq2. *Genome Biol.* doi: 10.1186/s13059-014-0550-8.
15. Bu D. et al., 2021. KOBAS-i: intelligent prioritization and exploratory visualization of biological functions for gene enrichment analysis. *Nucleic Acids Res.* doi: 10.1093/nar/gkab447.
 16. Ma Y. et al, 2024. Single cell protein production from methane in a gas-delivery membrane bioreactor. *Water Res.* doi: 10.1016/j.watres.2024.121820.
 17. He D. et al., 2019; The response of methanotrophs to additions of either ammonium, nitrate or urea in alpine swamp meadow soil as revealed by stable isotope probing; *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*; doi: 10.1093/femsec/fiz077
 18. Le Mer J. et al, 2001. Production, oxidation, emission and consumption of methane by soils: a review. *Eur J Soil Biol* doi: 10.1016/S1164-5563(01)01067-6.